

IoT Systems Testing Taxonomy - Experts' Perspectives.

We have developed the initial taxonomy to guide IoT systems practitioners. We reviewed 83 published papers about IoT systems testing, and we mined different testing terms. We classified those terms into 8 dimensions of testing IoT systems namely: **Why testing (why?)**, **What to test (what?)**, **How to test it (how?)**, **What stage of testing (when?)**, **What environment to use for testing (where?)**, **Who is responsible for testing (who?)**, **What artifacts and tools are needed (which?)**.

Furthermore, we initially contacted 18 industry practitioners with expertise in IoT systems to get their views, and we already included those views in our first version. Additionally, we are targeting more feedback from many other practitioners. We have identified you among the practitioners, and your expertise can help us to improve this taxonomy. If you have any question while filling this survey, you can contact me at mukizaenos@gmail.com.

Your information will be used only for the purpose of this survey and will not be disclosed. This research has received ethical certificate from Canada Research Chairs Secretariat.

The taxonomy can be found at : <https://sites.google.com/view/iotsystemtestingtaxonomy/home?authuser=6>

* Indique une question obligatoire

1. Adresse e-mail *

Participant Information

2. Your country of Birth *

3. Years of Experience in Software *

Une seule réponse possible.

- < 3 Years
- 3 to 5 Years
- 5 to 10 Years
- > 10 Years

4. Years of Experience in IoT systems *

Une seule réponse possible.

- < 3 Years
- 3 to 5 Years
- 5 to 10 Years
- > 10 Years

5. What is your current professional? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- Developer
- Tester or QA Engineer
- Business Analyst
- Project Manager
- Lead/Manager/Director
- Other

Overall structure and design of the proposed Taxonomy

6. Overall comment on the structure and design of this taxonomy *

7. Overall comment on the main categories and sub-categories *

8. Is the proposed taxonomy understandable and useful? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

9. If "No" explain why. If Yes, just write "Yes" *

10. Is the proposed taxonomy complete? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

11. If "No" explain why. If Yes, just write "Yes" *

12. Can the proposed taxonomy help the testers to understand all dimensions of testing? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

13. If "No" explain why. If Yes, just write "Yes" *

14. Can this taxonomy meets your expectations when testing IoT system? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

15. If "No" explain why. If Yes, just write "Yes" *

16. Can the proposed taxonomy have positive impact on effectiveness of testing IoT systems? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

17. If "No" explain why. If Yes, just write "Yes" *

Evaluation: Impact of the proposed taxonomy

18. Describe the overall impact of this taxonomy for IoT practitioners and stakeholders. *

19. Do you agree with objectives of testing? [Why testing (why?)] *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

20. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

21. Do you agree with aspects or components of IoT systems to be tested? [What to test (what?)]

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

22. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

23. Do you agree with recommended approaches or techniques recommended for testing IoT system? [How to test it (how?)] *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

24. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

25. Do you agree with the proposed timing of testing? [What stage of testing (when?)]

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

26. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

27. Do you agree with the proposed environment for testing? [What environment to * use for testing (where?)]

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

28. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

29. Do you agree with the proposed roles and responsibilities of individuals or teams involved in testing? [Who is responsible for testing (who?)] *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

30. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

31. Do you agree with artifacts and tools required to support the testing process? [What artifacts and tools are needed (which?)] *

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

32. If you answered "No" for the previous questions, explain what is missing.

33. Is there any missing category or sub categories for provided categories? If *
Yes, answer the next two questions.

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

34. What is the missing category and its possible sub-categories can you recommend to be added in the shared taxonomy? [Use empty line to separate categories if you recommend more than one]

35. For each proposed category in the shared taxonomy, write any missing sub-categories and any possible child in parent-child relationship. [Use empty line to separate categories]

36. Do you recommend any sub-category that can be moved from one category to another?

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

37. If you answered 'Yes' to the previous questions, which sub-category can be moved to where?. [Use empty line to separate categories]

38. Do you believe that this taxonomy will be useful for practitioners? *

Une seule réponse possible.

Strongly agree

Agree

Neutral

Disagree

Strongly disagree

39. How can you generate the test case for end-to-end testing scenario for IoT systems from the device to the application layer or vice-versa?(Describe your opinion if any [optional])

Ce contenu n'est ni rédigé, ni cautionné par Google.

Google Forms

